

An Empirical Analysis of the Flow of Islamic Banking and Economic Growth in Bahrain

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Abstract

Islamic banking and finance is one of the most rapidly growing segments of the global financial system and was expected to have a significant relationship and contribution towards the economic growth of any country. This paper explores empirically the relationship between the development of Islamic finance system and economic growth in kingdom of Bahrain. Using econometric analysis, annually time-series data of economic growth and Islamic banks' financing from 1990 to 2008 were used. We use Islamic banks' financing credited to private sector through modes of financing as a proxy for the development of Islamic finance system and Gross Domestic Product (GDP), as a proxy for economic growth. For the analysis, the unit root test, co-integration test and Granger causality tests were done. Our empirical results generally signify that in the long run Islamic banks' financing is positive and significantly correlated with economic growth in Bahrain which reinforces the idea that a well-functioning banking system promotes economic growth. The results obtained from Granger causality test reveals a positive and statistically significant relationship between economic growth and Islamic banks' financing in the long-term.

Key words: Islamic finance, Economic growth, Causality, Bahrain

1. Introduction

Islamic banking and development is growing as a source of finance for Islamic and other investors around the world. During the past years, one of the rising stars in the world of finance has been Islamic finance. The year 2013 marked a turning point for Islamic finance growth, as new markets and new regulations in the Mid East, helped the sector to flourish. The recent increased international attention on Islamic finance, post the financial crisis, presents a unique opportunity for the industry to further strengthen its appeal by attracting investors who are now turning to more ethical products.

It is a field of growing importance for conservative Muslims, especially in the Middle East and large Muslim population in South-Eastern Asia countries, who are uncomfortable with Western-style of financial system and banking that involve explicit payments of interest. Lately, the Vatican (2009) noted that Western banks should look at the rules of Islamic finance to restore confidence amongst their clients at a time of global economic crisis. Recently,

Ernst & Young's World Islamic Banking Competitiveness Report 2013 said global Islamic banking assets are expected to reach \$1.8tn by 2014, up from the \$1.3tn of assets held in 2011.

Neither the ongoing turmoil in the Middle East nor the Euro Zone debt crisis could prevent Islamic banks in the Middle East from reaching out to new markets and more business. This rapid growth has been fuelled by surging demand for Shariah (the path", term of Islamic law consists of Islamic instructions based on the Holy Quran and Sunnah) products not only from financiers in the Middle East and other Muslim countries, but also by investors globally, thus making it a global phenomenon. Despite the financial crisis which has plagued the economies of both industrialized and developing nations, the Islamic finance industry has been flourishing, and has enjoyed a 29 percent growth in assets to reach more than U.S.\$ 600 billion in 2008 (Figure1).

Fig.1 Global Shariah-Compliant Financial Assets 2000-2011)

Source: Deutsche Bank, (2011)

The relationship between financial development and economic growth has been extensively examined in the literature. Most empirical studies find that the former, together with a more efficient banking system, accelerates the latter. Levine (2005) suggested that financial institutions and markets can foster economic growth through several channels, i.e., by (i) easing the exchange of goods and services through the provision of payment of services, (ii) mobilizing and pooling savings from a large number of investors, (iii) acquiring and processing information about enterprises and possible investment projects, thus allocating savings to their most productive use, (iv) monitoring investment and carrying out corporate governance, and (v) diversifying, increasing liquidity and reducing risk. Each of these functions can influence saving and investment decisions, and hence economic growth.

Despite there are many studies examining the relationship between conventional finance and economic growth, the studies that examine the relationship between Islamic finance and economic growth are not too many. So, in this study, the relationship between the development of Islamic finance system and growth of the economy in Bahrain will be tested to see whether Islamic finance contribute to economic growth or not.

The paper is organized as follows. Section one gives a general introduction about the current stage of Islamic finance. Section two presents the growth of Islamic finance in Bahrain. Section three explains the research problem and objective. Section four illustrates the methodology of the research. Section five includes the literature review on the relationship between Finance and economic growth, and in particularly Islamic finance and economic growth. Section six explores the results and the analysis of the paper. Finally, section seven gives the conclusions of the paper.

2. Islamic Finance in Bahrain

Kingdom of Bahrain has the fastest growing economy in the Arab world (Arabian business, 2013). It also has the freest economy in the Middle East and is twelfth freest overall in the world based on the 2011 Index of Economic Freedom Bahrain's banking and financial services sector (Heritage website, 2013), particularly Islamic banking, have benefited from the regional boom driven by demand for oil. Petroleum production and processing account is Bahrain's most exported product, accounting for 60% of export receipts, 70% of government revenues, and 11% of GDP.

The banking sector in Bahrain benefited from rapid economic growth. As a result, Islamic banks posted strong results over the past few years. During the period expanding from 1990 till 2008, combined assets of all Islamic Banks generated a impressive increase from less than 7,000 U.S.\$ million in 1990 to more than U.S\$ Million 37,000 in 2008 with a cumulative increase up to 98.22 % as shown in figure 2.

Fig.2: Islamic Banks' Assets in Bahrain (1990- 2008)

Source: Developed by the researchers

In recent years, Bahrain has rapidly become a global leader in Islamic finance, playing host to the largest concentration of Islamic financial institutions in the Middle East. It is at the forefront in the market for Islamic bonds (Sukuk), including short-term government Sukuk as well as leasing securities. The Central Bank has played a leading role in the introduction of these innovative products. The market share of Islamic banks correspondingly increased from 1.8% of total banking assets in 2000 to 13.3% in August 2012. Islamic banks provide a variety of products, including Murabaha, Ijara, Mudaraba, Musharaka, Al Salam and Istitsna'a, restricted and unrestricted investment accounts, syndications and other structures. The Central Bank of Bahrain has installed a comprehensive prudential and reporting framework, tailor-made for the specific concepts and needs of Islamic banking and insurance. In addition to the numerous Islamic financial institutions active in its financial sector, Bahrain also plays a host to a number of organizations central to the development of Islamic finance, including: i) the Accounting and Auditing Organization for Islamic Financial Institutions (AAOIFI); ii) Liquidity Management Centre (LMC); iii) the International Islamic Financial Market (IIFM), iv) and the Islamic International Rating Agency (IIRA) and v) Shariah Review Bureau (Bahrain central bank report, 2013).

As of November 2008, there are 417 financial institutions in Bahrain, including 59 IFIs. The banking industry in Bahrain is the combination of both wholesale (investment

and retail (commercial banks) banking. The sector consists of 88 conventional banks (24 retail and 64 wholesale) and 26 Islamic banks. The financial sector has a 22% share in GDP, making it the second most important industry in the country. In 2007, total banking assets increased 31.2%, reaching U.S\$ Billion 245. During the first half of 2008, it increased 26.6% to U.S\$ Billion 101.5.

Bahrain's well structured Islamic banking system has caught the attention of many foreign companies. Islamic banking industry in Bahrain is expected to register moderate growth, on account of increased competition. The industry is well-supported by the regulator, which encourages innovation while providing sound regulatory framework (Blominvest report, 2009).

3. Research Problem and Objectives

There is no doubt that Islamic financial sector development plays an important role in the overall development of an economy. Although, there are many empirical studies that examined the relationship between finance and economic growth, but specific empirical studies on the relationship between Islamic finance and economic growth, are not too many. So, this study tries to examine empirically the relationship between Islamic finance and economic growth, and its direction in Bahrain.

4. Research Methodology

The qualitative and quantitative methods have been used. The data set is extracted from World Trade organization, Global Development Finance and Islamic Banks and Financial Institutions Information (IBIS) database for all Islamic banks' financing in Bahrain. To serve our purpose, appropriate variables were established and the long term relationships between those variables are determined by using econometric estimation methods. We use annually time series data from 1990 to 2008 for the variables. Islamic bank' financing through modes of financing as a proxy for financial sector and Real Gross Domestic Product (GDP) as a proxy for economic growth were used.

The first step of the study is to determine the relationship between financial deepening and economic growth, and whether the series are stationary or not. In a model, for a correct evaluation, time series should be separated from all effects, and the series should be stationary. Thus, logarithms of time series were taken. Augmented Dickey Fuller (1981) and Phillips Perron (1988) tests are used. After that, Johansen co-integration test was used to examine the long-term relationship between financial deepening and economic growth. And then, the Granger causality test is used to test the causality between Islamic bank financing and economic growth. We use Eviews software to test and analyze the results.

5. Literature Review

The relationship between financial development and economic growth has been extensively analysed in the literature. The relationship between financial development and economic growth is a controversial issue. Some authors consider finance an important element of growth (Schumpeter, 1934; Goldsmith, 1969; McKinnon, 1973, Shaw, 1973; King and Levine (1993), whilst for others it is only a minor growth factor (Robinson, 1952; Lucas, 1988). Schumpeter (1934) sees the banking sector as an engine of economic growth through its funding of productive investment. On the contrary, Lucas (1988) argues that the role of finance has been overstressed.

According to the theory, the development of the banking industry is favourable to the economic growth because the activity of the banks increases the mobilization of the saving, improves the efficiency of the resources allowance, and stimulates the technological innovation. Most studies (including recent ones) argue, in accordance with the theoretical predictions that, there is a positive relation between the financial development and the economic growth. Beck et al (2000), Bekaert et al (2001) and Levine (2005) strongly supported the idea that there is a positive relationship between financial development and economic growth.

With regard to the relationship between Islamic financial development and economic growth, Abduh and Omar (2012), Furqani and Mulyany (2009) and Majid and Kassim (2008) are among the limited studies in this area. Abduh and Omar (2012) identifies that the relationship is bi-directional.

Therefore, the government policies in supporting the development of Islamic finance in Indonesia are strongly needed in order to support the economic development. However, using different time span of quarterly data, findings from Furqani and Mulyany (2009) and Majid and Kassim (2008) are different in terms of the direction of the relationship. Furqani and Mulyany (2009), on the one hand, states that the relationship between Islamic financial development and economic growth is following the view of "demand-following" which means that growth in real sector economy stimulates Islamic banking institutions to change and develop. On the contrary, finding from Majid and Kassim (2008) is in favour of the supply-leading view.

6. Analysis and Results:

6.1 Descriptive Statistics

Table (1) presents summary statistics about the variables used in the econometric analysis for Bahrain. Figure 3 shows the relationship between Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and Islamic banks' financing in Bahrain graphically.

Table 1: Summary Statistics (1990-2008)

Statistics (US \$ Millions)	GDP	IBF
Mean	8,975.566	2,143.789
Median	6,621.190	1,071.000
Maximum	21,902.89	11,632.00
Minimum	4,229.790	0.339.0000
Std. Dev.	5,034.908	2,852.508
observations	19	19

Fig.3 GDP and IBF Growth in Bahrain (1990-2008)
Source: Developed by researchers

From table 1, we notice that the maximum value for IBFinancing in 2008 reached to 11,632.00 from 0,339.00 in 1990 with standard deviation of 2,852.508. This gives us an indication of high growth of the Islamic finance industry in the recent years. The statistics show that the median for GDP and IBFinancing is less than the mean, which indicates that the values are positively skewed. Figure 3 shows that when Islamic Banks’ financing goes up, the GDP also goes up which indicates that the positive relationship between the two variables.

6.2 Unit Root Test

Results of ADF and PP Tests applied to time series show that all series belong to economic growth and financial deepening indicators are not stationary at level. To make that series stationary, first differences of series have been taken. Failure to reject the null hypothesis of unit roots implies that the linear combination of the variables is non-stationary; hence we cannot pursue for the cointegration tests. ADF Test results are shown in Table 2:
 The results of the table 2 indicate that the data at the first difference is stationary at α 1%, 5%, and 10% level of significance respectively. For GDP variable, if p value is less than α , then H_0 is rejected, and the series is stationary. From table 2, the first row shows that the p value (0.0413) is less than α (0.05) in ADF test. Similarly, for IBFinancing, the result from the second row shows that the p value (0.0087) is less than α (0.05). This suggests that the null hypothesis is rejected for both variables. Hence, the failure to reject the alternative hypothesis indicates that the two series are stationary.

6.3 Johansen Co-integration Test

Table 3 shows the results of Johansson test for the long relationship between Islamic banks’ financing and economic growth. The trace test rejects the null hypothesis if the trace statistics exceeds the critical value.

The first row of table 3 shows that the trace statistics (34.66095) exceeds the critical value of (15.41) at 95 percent confidence level. It suggests that the null hypothesis of no cointegrating relationships is rejected. The results confirm that there is a cointegrating relationship among the variables. The eigenvalue test, tests the null hypothesis of r versus r+1 cointegrating relationships. This test rejects the null hypothesis if the eigenvalue test statistics exceeds the respective critical value. Table 4 presents the results from this test. Similarly, the result from the first row of table 4 shows that the eigenvalue test statistics (22.62951) exceeds the critical value (14.07) at 95 percent confidence level. This suggests that the null hypothesis is rejected. Hence, the failure to reject the alternative hypothesis indicates that there is one cointegrating relationship among the variables.

The results from table 3 and 4, if read together, show that the null hypotheses of non-cointegration are rejected at 5 percent level of significance. This suggests that in the long run Islamic banks’ financing will contribute in the growth of GDP of Bahrain.

Table 2: Unit Root Test

		ADF Test		Phillip-Person Test	
		Level 1	First difference	Level 1	First difference
Country	Variable	t- statistic P value	t- statistic P value	t- statistic P value	t- statistic P value
Bahrain	GDP	0.529475 0.9984	-3.821091 0.0413**	0.897097 0.9995	-3.893848 0.0363**
	IBFinancing	-1.266411 0.8631	-4.695598** 0.0087	-1.266411 0.8631	-4.695598** 0.0087
*, **, *** significant at 1%, 5%, 10% level respectively					

Table 3: Johansen's test (trace statistic)

		Trace statistics	Critical values	
			5%	1%
Null hypothesis	Ho: r = 0	34.66095	15.41	20.04
Alternative hypothesis	H1: r ≥ 1	12.03144	3.76	6.65
Co-integration Equation	GDP = 0.449203 IBF			
** significant at 5 % level				

Table 4: Johansen's test (Max-Eigenvalue statistic)

		Max-Eigenvalue	Critical values	
			5%	1%
Null hypothesis	Ho: r = 0	22.62951	14.07	18.63
Alternative hypothesis	H1: r = 1	12.03144	3.76	6.65
Co-integration Equation	GDP = 0.449203 IBF			
** significant at 5 % level				

6.4 Granger Causality Test

Statistics and probability values constructed under the null hypothesis of non-causality are reported in Table 5. It can be observed that there is a causal relationship between Islamic banks' financing and economic growth. However, our results show that two-way causality exists from Islamic banks' financing to economic growth and from GDP

towards Islamic Banks' financing, since the probability values 0.04321 and 0.02478 are less than 0.05. So, the null hypothesis is rejected, and it can be concluded that the higher flow of Islamic finance has led to the growth of the economy. At the same time, the development of the real sector economy stimulates Islamic banking institutions to change and develop.

Table 5: Pair wise Granger Causality Tests (1990-2008)

Null Hypothesis	F statistics	Probability
IBF does not Granger Cause GDP	4.87614	0.04321**
GDP does not Granger Cause IBF	6.22222	0.02478**
** Significant at 5 % level		

7. Conclusion

This paper makes an attempt to examine the relationship between the development of Islamic finance and economic growth in the long-term in kingdom of Bahrain. We analyzed empirically the relationship between Islamic banks' financing and economic growth. Since, the variables in this paper are non-stationary; therefore, the Johansen's co-integration technique has been applied. The co-integration results provide evidence of a unique cointegrating vector. In other words, there is a long-term stable relationship between Islamic banks' financing and

economic growth in Bahrain. That means Islamic banks' financing and economic growth move together in the long-run. It is proved that the Bahrain has benefited from strong banking system. We also find that the causality relation exist in a bi-directional relationship from Islamic banks' financing to economic growth and vice versa .Our results also indicate that improvement of the Islamic financial institutions in the Bahrain will benefit from economic development, and it is important in the long run for the economic welfare, and also for poverty reduction. The results of study are quite significant as it is one of the pioneering studies of Islamic finance.

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